

e- ISSN: 3048-5665

Volume 09 Issue 02
May-Aug, 2026

*Corresponding Author:
*Krishna S, Student,
Department of
Information Science and
Engineering, PESITM,
Shivamogga, India*

Exploring Generative AI for Voice-Driven Interfaces: A Literature Review

Enosh R S¹, Krishna S², Manjunatha H M³, Niranjana Naik P K⁴, Ramesh D⁵

¹⁻⁴Student, ⁵Guide, Department of Information Science and Engineering, PESITM, Shivamogga, India

ABSTRACT

Voice-driven interfaces are evolving rapidly due to continuous advancements in generative artificial intelligence. The paper examines that how generative AI technologies work together with voice user interfaces and studies the relationship between them. It discusses the existing research along with the underlying technical frameworks while addressing usability aspects, ethical concerns, and possible future developments. Then the review together brings insights from recent studies to emphasize the key challenges as well as the new opportunities that can guide designers and researchers working in this area.

Keywords: *Generative AI, voice user interface, VUI, human-computer interaction, user experience, multimodal interaction*

1. INTRODUCTION

Human-machine interaction has slowly shifted from command-line and graphical modes to more natural and intuitive interfaces. Voice user interfaces (VUIs) have been particularly promising as they allow hands-free, conversational interactions [5]. At the same time, generative AI, including large language models, generative audio, and multimodal models, has developed enough to support new types of interfaces. These interfaces can move beyond scripted responses to engage in dynamic, context-aware dialogue [4]. The convergence can present opportunities for voice-driven interfaces that are more adaptive, personalized, and seamless.

The purpose of the paper is to review the literature on how generative AI is being integrated into voice-driven interfaces. We will discuss proposed architectures, usability and ethical issues that arise, and any remaining gaps. We organize the review into several sections: background concepts in Section II, architectural and technical frameworks in Section III, user experience and usability concerns in Section IV, ethical, privacy, and accessibility aspects in Section V, and future research directions in Section VI. A conclusion follows background Concepts.

Voice User Interfaces (VUIs)

Voice user interfaces allow interaction through spoken input and system responses. They become more common with the digital assistants and smart

devices [5]. VUIs provide benefits like hands-free interaction, accessibility for the users with limited mobility, and natural language as a way to communicate. However, they also encounter known challenges in speech recognition accuracy, context retention, turn-taking behavior, and managing user expectations [1].

Generative AI

Generative AI refers to machine-learning models can create new content, such as text, audio, images, and even video. These models do more than just perform classification or prediction tasks. In the context of interfaces, generative AI provides dynamic responses, adjusts to user behaviour, generates personalized content, and allows for multimodal interaction [2]. For voice interfaces, generative audio synthesis, like waveform generation, and large-language-model (LLM) dialogue generation are especially important [13].

Why Combine Generative AI + VUIs?

By combining VUIs with generative AI, systems can shift from fixed command-response patterns to more natural, conversational, and context-aware interactions. For time being, generative models can create spoken responses in real-time, tailor voice tone, adjust to user preferences, and manage open-ended questions instead of being restricted to predefined scripts [4]. This opens up the potential for genuinely natural voice-driven interfaces.

Fig.1

The figure illustrates the working architecture of a Voice-Driven Interface (VDI), showing how spoken communication between a user and the system occurs in a continuous loop. The process begins when the user's will start the speech signal and is converted to text through the Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) technique. Text is then interpreted by the Natural Language Understanding (NLU) to extract its meaning, which is processed by the Interaction Management module to determine an appropriate response. The response is transformed into text by Natural Language Generation (NLG) and finally converted back into speech through Speech Synthesis, completing the interaction cycle. Overall, the diagram highlights the flow from speech input to understanding, response generation, and synthesized output, forming the foundation for intelligent voice-based communication systems [1,2,4].

Architectures and Technical Frameworks

- **Stack Components**

A typical generative AI voice user interface stack includes: [1] automatic speech recognition (ASR) technique will

convert spoken input into text, [2] natural language understanding (NLU) to interpret intent, [3] a generative model (LLM or specialized dialogue model) that creates an appropriate response, and [4] text-to-speech (TTS) or a generative audio module that turns response text into spoken output. Additional modules may include context memory, user modelling, multimodal fusion (voice, gesture, and vision), and trade-offs between on-device and cloud processing. For example, recent research on multimodal generative AI in user interfaces highlights the need to combine voice, text, and video streams into a single framework. It also addresses the "interface dilemma" of choosing between voices, graphical user interface, or mixed modalities.

- **On-Device vs Cloud Processing**

One key challenge is deciding if generative components should run on the device (mobile or embedded) or in the cloud. On-device processing provides lower latency and improved privacy, but it has limits in computing power and memory. Cloud processing can handle larger models, but it comes with latency, reliance on connectivity, and privacy issues [4].

- ***Adaptation and Personalization***

Generative AI allows systems to personalize voice output, such as tone and style. It can modify response content based on a user's profile or history. It can even create new functions by learning. However, implementing this needs careful user modelling, memory management that considers context, and stability against user variation [2].

- ***Evaluation Metrics***

Technical evaluation includes ASR accuracy, dialogue coherence, response latency, user satisfaction, error recovery, and multimodal synchrony. Recent reviews point out to the studies on voice interface usability still lack consistent metrics and frameworks [5].

User Experience and Usability

User-experience (UX) is critical for voice-driven generative systems. Studies show that while users appreciate the convenience of VUIs, the unpredictability of generative responses can raise issues of trust, comprehension, and control [5]. For instance, if the system generates an unexpected or inappropriate answer, user satisfaction declines.

- ***Interaction Quality***

Research finds that factors like speech recognition accuracy, response latency, clarity of voice output, and turn-taking behavior operation strongly affect the people perceive the quality of VUIs [5]. When generative AI is added, new factors come into play. These include consistency of style, coherence across turns, avoiding "hallucinations" (i.e., false generated responses), and meeting user expectations.

- ***Accessibility and Inclusion***

Voice interfaces can greatly improve the accessibility for users with visual or by the motor impairments. Generative AI

can personalize these interfaces for users, such as by creating voices with specific profiles or adjusting vocabulary. Study highlighted the using voice for direct manipulation in intent-driven interfaces is a promising way to promote inclusion [9].

- ***Human-AI Collaboration***

Even in voice mode, users often expect some control. They may want to step in, rephrase, or switch to manual mode. Designing generative voice user interfaces involves creating a way for users to work together with the system. The system suggests, and the user refines. This matches with human-AI collaboration ideas found in recent generative AI literature [3].

2. FUTURE RESEARCH ENHANCEMENT

Our review, the following research avenues are prominent:

Robustness to Open-Ended Queries: Generative systems must handle unexpected user utterances, ambiguous context and domain shifts gracefully.

Multimodal Fusion: Combining voice with gesture, vision and touch to build richer interfaces [4].

On-Device Generative Models: Developing efficient, low-latency generative voice systems deployable on mobile or embedded hardware.

Personalised Voice Experience: Research into adaptive voice profiles, user-styling, emotional tone, and long-term memory in voice interactions.

Ethics and Safe Generative Voice: Ensuring generated voice behaviour is ethical, private, transparent and inclusive.

Evaluation Frameworks: Developing standard metrics and methodologies specific to generative voice-driven interfaces (coherence, trust, accessibility).

Real-World Deployment Studies:

Longitudinal studies of generative VUIs in the wild (smart homes, cars, wearables) to understand adoption, errors, user behaviour.

3. CONCLUSION

The combination of generative AI and voice-driven interfaces will offers the exciting possibilities of creating more natural, flexible, and conversational systems. There are major challenges related to technology, usability, ethics, and accessibility. This review has examined important literature, identified design patterns, pointed out user experience issues, and suggested future paths. As research continues, designers and engineers can collaborate closely with HCI, ethics, and domain experts to develop voice interfaces are not only the intelligent but also trustworthy, inclusive, and focused on human needs.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to sincerely thank the principal, management, and the Department of Information Science and Engineering at PES Institute of Technology and Management, Shivamogga, for their invaluable support and encouragement throughout the undertaking of this literature survey. Their guidance and resources have been instrumental in enabling this research effort.

REFERENCES

1. Zhang, C., He, J., Wang, M., & Zhang, Y. (2023). A survey on audio diffusion models: Text-to-speech synthesis and enhancement in generative AI. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2307.04670*.
2. Bieniek, J., Rahouti, M., & Verma, D. C. (2024). Generative AI in multimodal user interfaces: Trends, challenges, and cross-platform adaptability. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.02043*.
3. Papneja, H., & Yadav, N. (2024). Self-disclosure to conversational AI: A literature review, emergent framework, and directions for future research. *Computers in Human Behavior Reports, 12*, 101–119.
4. Nayak, M., Kangas, J., & Raisamo, R. (2025). A study of NLP-based speech interfaces in medical virtual reality. *Multimodal Technologies and Interaction, 9*(1), 18–29.
5. Genelza, G. G. (2024). A systematic literature review on AI voice cloning generator: A game-changer or a threat? *Journal of Emerging Technologies, 14*(2), 53–70.
6. Zhang, Y., Lin, H., & Kang, L. (2025). AI versus human-generated voices and avatars: Rethinking user engagement and cognitive load. *Education and Information Technologies, 30*, 223–242.
7. Urzúa, C. A. C., Martinez, A., & Perez, D. (2025). Effects of AI-assisted feedback via generative chat on academic writing: A systematic review. *Education Sciences, 15*(4), 1–21.
8. Alabduljabbar, R. (2024). User-centric AI: Evaluating the usability of generative AI applications through user reviews on app stores. *PeerJ Computer Science, 11*, 1–16.
9. dos Santos, A., Souza, R. V., & Silva, M. P. (2024). An automated literature survey of data-driven speech enhancement methods. *Acta Acustica, 110*(1), 88–102.
10. Mundra, R., Kohli, J., & Bhatt, P. (2024). Value to user's voice: A generative AI framework for actionable insights from customer reviews. In *Proceedings of ICON 2024* (pp. 351–359).
11. Deshmukh, A. M. (2024). User experience and usability of voice user interfaces: A systematic literature review. *Information, 15*(5), 579–601.
12. Rakotomalala, F., Hajalalaina, A. R., Niriarijaona, H. N., &

- Ravonimanantsoa, N. M. V. (2022). Voice user interface: Literature review, challenges and future directions. Laboratory for Mathematics and Computer Applied to the Development Systems (LIMAD), University of Fianarantsoa.
13. Ordoumpozanis, K., & Papadopoulou, M. (2024). Generative artificial intelligence for speech and dialogue systems: Emerging trends and applications. *IEEE Access*, *12*, 134762–134779.
 14. Colazzo, L., Pucci, E., & Matera, M. (2025). Voice-based direct manipulation to foster inclusion in intent-driven user interfaces. *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*, *3836*, 115–126.
 15. Seymour, W., Zhan, X., Cote, M., & Such, J. (2022). A systematic review of ethical concerns with voice assistants. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2208.05701*.